

Relationship of Third Molar Position on Condylar Fractures: A Series of 80 Cases

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Abstract:

Background: The mandible is one of the most susceptible facial bones to fracture; this is due to its relatively prominent position to common injuring forces. Condylar region of the mandible is one of the vulnerable sites to fracture due to its anatomical weakness. Fractures of the mandibular condyle are common and mandibular third molars are frequently implicated in their pathogenesis. Condylar fracture comprises a large percentage of mandible fracture and many studies have been conducted in several countries. Moderate force leads to condylar fracture when the third molar is completely erupted or unerupted without development of root or absent.

Objective: The aim of this study was to determine the relationship between the third molar position and the mandibular condylar fractures.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery in Dhaka Dental College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh, from January-2016 to June 2016. A total of 80 patients attended to OPD or admitted to hospital with condyle of the mandible fracture (Patients having with or without presence or absence of mandibular third molar) irrespective of age and sex were enrolled in this study through purposive sampling technique. The collected data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version-23.0. Chi-square test was performed to determine the relationship between third molars' position and the level of condylar fracture where $p < 0.05$ considered as the level of significance with 95% CI. The ethical clearance of this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Dhaka Dental College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Results: This study evaluated 80 noted patients with mandibular condylar fracture. Within 80 condylar fractured patients 74 (12.5%) have mandibular third molar. 6 (7.5%) didn't have third molar, majority of the patients were male 58 (72.5%). The majority of the patients 41 (51.25%) belonged to the age group (30-39) years and the mean age of the study patients was 40.39 ± 10.24 years. The cause of injury were noted road traffic accidents 50 (62.5%) was the main cause of fracture, data regarding occupation showed 42 (52.5%) were service holders. Data of the current study shows that, within 80 patients with mandibular condyle fracture among them 45 (61.25%) were non-displaced condylar fracture. Among 74 patients with third molar, 28 (37.8%) had impacted third molar and 46 (62.2%) had erupted third molar. In the present study, mandibular condylar fractures were more frequent (62.25%) in the erupted mandibular third molars as compared to these with unerupted ones. This study revealed that the risk of condylar fractures was also dependent on unerupted third molar position. The highest occurrence of condylar fracture was in class I 49 (61.25%) and position A 42 (52.50%) as well as according to Winter's classification, vertical angulation 14 (50.0%) was more frequent followed by mesio-angulation 7 (25.0%). The results of this study demonstrate that when the third molar is completely erupted, condyle has the tendency to fracture especially the sub condylar region. Simultaneously the results showed that when the tooth was in a vertical position the condylar fracture was classified as low and when in a mesio-angula: position it was classified as high. Finally, a significant relationship was observed between the third molar position and the mandibular condylar fractures ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The presence of unerupted lower third molar greatly reduces the occurrences of mandibular condylar fracture. The presence of erupted 3rd molar is a risk factor for mandibular condyle fracture and absence of it may increase the risk of condyle fracture and the position of the third molar is significantly related to condyle fractures.

Key words: Relationship, Third-molar, Position, condyle, Fractures, Mandible.

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Introduction

Mandible is the only mobile bone of the facial skeleton which plays an important role in mastication, speech and deglutition. Being a prominent bone of the facial skeleton, it is one of the most common facial bone to be fractured. Fracture in the mandible causes severe loss of function and disfigurement [1]. Mandibular fractures follow a pattern, common to many injuries, in that young males are predominantly affected [2]. The incidence of mandible fracture is effected by several factor including the patients age, sex and socio-economic as well as the etiology. The direction & type of force is important in mandible fracture. Fracture mandible may result from direct violence, indirect violence and excessive Lateral muscular constriction. Fracture displacement at condyle is influenced pterygoid muscle. Fracture in this region have been classified as intracapsular or high capsular fracture and extra capsular or low or subcondylar fracture. The causes of fracture of the mandible are chiefly road traffic accidents, inter personal violence, falls, and sports injuries and industrial trauma. Road traffic accident is the leading cause of mandibular fracture in third world countries, while interpersonal violence is the leading cause in developed countries [3]. The study conducted in Bangladesh reported that the major causes of mandible fractures were road traffic accident (58.4%), other causes falls (13.6%), work related (12.8%), sports related (4.8%), assault (0.8%), altercation (8.0%) and pathological fracture (1.6%). Mandible fractures occur at various locations like body, angle, condyle, coronoid, and ramus and dentoalveolar region. Among the mandibular fractures body accounts 30.2%, angle 18.5%, condyle 11.2%, symphysis 25.3%, ramus 1.9% and dentoalveolar 9.8% fracture [4]. Mandibular fracture patterns depend on multiple factors, including direction and amount of force, presence of soft tissue bulk and bio-mechanical characteristics of the mandible such as bone density and mass or anatomic structures creating weak areas [5]. Many investigations reported that patients with unerupted mandibular third molars related to angle fracture are more than those patients without unerupted mandibular third molars. This has been attributed to the decreased amount of bone at the mandibular angle that contains the unerupted third molar [6-8]. An inverse relationship was seen for condylar fractures: patients with impacted mandibular third molars were less likely to have a condylar fracture

than those without impacted ones [9]. However, several authors recommended extraction of them in adolescents and young adults who frequently play contact sports because of the associated high incidence of mandibular angle fractures[10,11].As the mandible is fractured more often at the condyle rather than at the angle in the absence of unerupted third molars, it may not be advantageous to extract the unerupted third molars as a protective measure against mandibular angle fracture, because the treatment of condylar fracture is more difficult and challenging than that of angle fractures[12]. The objective of this study was to determine the relationship between the occurrence of mandibular condylar fracture and the presence and absence of unerupted mandibular third molars position.

Methods

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted at the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery in Dhaka Dental College and Hospital from January-2016 to June 2016. Written informed consent was taken from every patient explaining the nature and objectives of the study and a total of 80 patients attended to OPD or admitted to hospital with condyle of the mandible fracture (Patients having with or without presence or absence of mandibular third molar) irrespective of age and sex were enrolled in this study through purposive sampling technique. A standardized structured questionnaire was used to collect necessary information of the subject group. To evaluate the influence of incompletely erupted mandibular third molars on condylar fractures, the patients were divided in to two groups: those with incompletely erupted mandibular third molars. The later group included those with fully erupted or missing mandibular third molars. By using panoramic radiographs of 80 patients with incompletely erupted mandibular third molars, their positions were analyzed according to the Pell and Gregory and Winters classification. Pell and Gregory's classification was done according to the relationship of the impacted lower third molar to the ramus of the mandible and the second molar (Based on the space available distal to the second molar). The amount of horizontal space is measured between the anterior border of the ascending ramus and the posterior border of lower 2nd molar. When adequate space available, Class 1 impaction; when inadequate space available, Class 2 impaction and when third molar located all or mostly within the ascending ramus, class 3 impaction. Winter's classification was done according to vertical depth and angulation. The vertical space was

classified based on the highest position of the mandibular third molar crown with 2nd molar as follows: Class A, level at or above the occlusal plane; Class B, between the cement-enamel junction of the adjacent second molar and the occlusal plane; Class C, below the cement enamel junction. In addition, according to angulation, impacted third molar is classified based on the position of the impacted third molar to the long axis of the second molar. The collected data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version-23.0. Chi-square test was performed to determine the relationship between third molars' position and the level of condylar fracture where $p < 0.05$ considered as the level of significance with 95% CI. The ethical clearance of this study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Dhaka Dental College and Hospital, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients having mandibular condyle fracture with or without third molar.
2. Age limit of the patients were 17 years to 65 years of both sex.
3. Cooperative patients.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Patients who refused to be included in this study.
2. Patients having pathological condylar fracture.
3. Non-cooperative and psychic patient.
4. Edentulous patient.

Results

Table-I
Distribution of the study subjects by age (N=80)

Age groups(years)	Frequency	Percent
≤30 years	10	12.5
30-39 Years	41	51.25
40-49 Years	15	18.75
50-59 Years	11	13.75
> 60 Years	3	3.75
Total	80	100
Mean age(years)	40.39±10.24	
Age range (years)	17-65	

Table-I presents the age distribution of the study patients. Among the 80 patients, the most frequent age group was 30-39 years which includes 41 (51.25%) patients, followed by 40-49 years 15 (18.75%), <30 years 10 (12.5%), 50-59 years

11(13.75%) and >60 years 3(3.75%). The mean age of the study patients was 40.39 ± 10.24 years, with an age range spanning from 17 to 65 years.

Table-II

Distribution of the study subjects by sex (N=80).

Sex	Frequency	Percent
Male	58	72.5
Female	22	27.5
Total	80	100

Male: female ratio 2.6:1

Table-II shows the distribution of the study subjects by sex. The majority of the patients 58 (72.5%) were male and 22(27.5%) were female. Male: female ratio 2.6:1. Male patients were predominant in this current study.

Figure 1: *Distribution of the study subjects by occupation (N=80).*

Fig-1 illustrates the distribution of the study patients by occupation. The most frequent 42 (52.5%) patients were service holders followed by housewife 17(21.3%), business 13(16.3%) and others occupation were 8(10%).

Figure 2: *Distribution of the study subjects by cause of injury (N=80).*

Fig-2 shows the distribution of the study patients by cause of injury. The majority 50(62%) patients reported road traffic accident (RTA) followed by assault 20(25%), fall from height 5(6%), sport 3(4%) and industrial 2(3%).

Table-III
Status of third molar teeth with the study patients (N=80)

Status of third molar	Frequency	Percent
Present	74	92.5
Absent / Missing	6	7.5
Total	80	100

Table-3 shows the distribution of the study patients by status of third molar teeth with the study patients. The most frequent 74(92.5%) reported to have third molar teeth and 6(7.5%) didn't have third molar teeth. The finding signifies that, present of third molar teeth might precipitate the fracture in the condyle of mandible.

Table-IV
Condition of third molar (present) teeth (n = 74).

Condition of teeth	Frequency	Percent
Impacted	28	37.8
Erupted	46	62.2
Total	74	100

Table-4 shows the distribution of the study subjects by condition of third molar among the 74 patients with third molar teeth, 28 (37.8%) patients had impacted teeth and 46 (62.2%) patients had erupted teeth.

Table-V
The status of condyle fracture observed with study patients (n=80).

Status of fracture	Frequency	Percent
Non displaced	49	61.25
Displaced	24	30
Dislocated	7	8.75
Total	80	100

Table-5 shows the distribution of the patient by status of condyle fracture with the study patients. Among them 49 (61.25%) were non-displaced fracture, 24(30%) were displaced fracture and 7(8.755) were dislocated fracture.

Table-VI
Influence of lower third molar position on condylar fractures (N=80).

Third molar position	Frequency	Percent
Class- I	49	61.25
Class- II	26	32.5
Class- III	5	6.25
Class- A	42	52.5
Class- B	29	36.25
Class- C	9	11.25

Table-6 shows the influence of tooth position on the occurrence of condylar fracture. Most of the condylar fractures were associated with class- I which includes 49(61.25%) of the patients followed by class-II, 26(32.5%) and class-III, 5(6.25%), while the most frequent class A were 42(52.50%), class-B, 29(36.25%) and class-C, 9(11.25%).

Table-VII
Relation of third molars' position with the level of condylar fracture (n=80).

Third molar position	N	High capsular condylar No. (%)	Sub (low) condylar No. (%)	P value
Erupted	46	5(10.9%)	41(89.1%)	0.013 ^S
Unerrupted /Impreted	28	10(35.7%)	18(64.3%)	
Absent	6	0(0.0%)	6(100.0%)	
Total	80	15(18.8%)	65(81.2%)	

Table-7 shows the relation of third molars' position with the level of condylar fracture. Among the study patients, sub-condylar region had the more tendency to fracture when third molar was erupted. Among 46 erupted cases 41(89.1%) had sub (low) condylar fracture and among unerupted 28 cases 18(64.3%) were sub (low) condylar. Sub condylar fracture is significantly more than high capsular condylar ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

Condylar region of the mandible is one of the most common susceptible sites to fracture. This study sets out to evaluate the relation between 3rd molar and condyle fracture. This study evaluated 80 noted patients with mandibular condylar fracture and compares the results of previous studies. Within 80 condylar fractured patients 74(92.5%) have mandibular third molar, 6(7.5%) didn't have third

molar, majority of the patients were male 58(72.5%), maximum patients 41(51.25%) age was between (30-39) years and mean age 40.39 ± 10.24 years. The cause of injury were noted road traffic accidents 50(62.5%) was the main cause of fracture, data regarding occupation show 42(52.5%) were service holders. Data of the current study shows that, within 80 patients with mandibular condyle fracture among them 49(61.25%) were non-displaced condylar fracture. Among 74 patients with third molars, 28(37.8%) have impacted third molar and 46(62.2%) have erupted third molar. A biomechanical study showed that condyle area is the weakest against the impact acting on the mandible, especially at the anterior region [13]. The impact forces that cause condylar fractures transmit to the mandibular angle on the same side, which is biomechanically stronger than the condyle. In the group of condylar fracture, the results of this study agree with in relation to the prevalence of an older population [14], but in relation to the predominant gender, which was male in this study. The greater predisposition of male was probably due to the fact that they are more exposed to the risk factors for facial trauma, such as road accidents and physical aggression. Clinical investigations have implied that unerupted mandibular third molar is a risk factor for mandibular angle fractures [15]. The reason for the higher risk of angle fractures in cases with unerupted mandibular third molars is thought to be that the mandibular angle is weakened by the decrease in bony space caused by presence of the tooth. In the present study, mandibular condylar fractures were more frequent (62.25%) in those erupted mandibular third molars as compared to those with unerupted ones. Similar result was found by Kumar SR et al. (2015) in their study patients with erupted 3rd molar were two times more likely to have condylar fracture than those with unerupted third molars [16]. Our findings come in agreement with other previous studies in that incompletely erupted mandibular third molars are preventive factors against condylar fractures [17, 18]. This study revealed that the risk of condylar fractures was also dependent on unerupted third molar position. The highest occurrence of condylar fracture was in class I 49(61.25%) and position A 42(52.50%) as well as according to Winter's classification, vertical angulation 14(50.0%) was more frequent followed by mesio-angulation 7(25.0%). One study reported, percentage of class A, vertical impaction was more,

class I 49(61.25%) and position A 42(52.50%) as well as according to Winter's classification, vertical angulation 14(50.0%) was more frequent followed by mesio-angulation 7(25.0%)[19]. The results of this study demonstrate that when the third molar is completely erupted, condyle has the tendency to fracture especially the sub condylar region. Simultaneously the results showed that when the tooth was in a vertical position the condylar fracture was classified as low and when in a mesio-angular position it was classified as high. These findings are in agreement with a recent study [20]. Clinically, patients with mandibular angle fractures generally do not experience severe postoperative complications. In contrast, condylar process fractures have a risk of functional, such as malocclusion and decreased mandibular mobility [21]. Other authors have suggested extraction of unerupted mandibular third molars in young sports-men as preventive measures against mandibular angle fractures [22, 23]. However, this treatment policy may possibly alter the biomechanical strength of the mandible and increase the risk of condylar fractures. In terms of the precise reduction and fixation of mandibular fractures, difficulties are often encountered in repositioning the condylar fragments and performing placement of the plates and screws, in addition, there is the possibility of facial nerve injury [24]. Excellent reduction and stable fixation in angle fractures are easily performed because the access and visibility to the angle fracture for plating is much better. Thus it might not be appropriate to strengthen the mandibular angle region and to make the mandible more vulnerable to condylar fractures by removing the unerupted third molars because the treatment of condylar fractures is more challenging than that of angle [25].

Limitations of the Study

This study was conducted with a purposive sampling technique, which may have introduced selection bias and limited the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the relatively small sample size (80 patients) and the study's confinement to a single center in Dhaka, Bangladesh, may not adequately represent broader populations or account for regional variations in third molar position and mandibular condylar fractures.

Conclusion

The presence of unerupted lower third molar greatly reduces the occurrences of mandibular condylar

fracture. The presence of erupted 3rd molar is a risk factor for mandibular condyle fracture and absence of it may increase the risk of condyle fracture and the position of the third molar is significantly related to condyle fractures.

Recommendations

It is recommended that future studies involve larger, more diverse populations across multiple centers to confirm the relationship between third molar position and mandibular condylar fractures. Advanced imaging and biomechanical studies should also be utilized to better understand the mechanisms behind these fractures. Clinicians should carefully assess the presence and position of third molars when evaluating fracture risks and consider these factors in trauma prevention and management strategies.

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